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THE INTRICACIES OF CROSS-CULTURAL ENCOUNTERS IN JOSEPH CONRAD'S *ALMAYER'S FOLLY*

Yu-Miao Yang

Indigenous Studies in Communication & Design, I-Shou University
No.1, Sec. 1, Syuecheng Rd.
Dashu District, Kaohsiung City 84001, TAIWAN
Email: yyangp@isu.edu.tw

ABSTRACT

Seeing the colonial adventures through the eyes of European conquerors, cross-cultural encounters often proved to be problematic experience, for, confined in an alien settlement without any familiar civilised artefacts nor social network to assist the daily remembrance of who they are, the colonialists often fell to the pray of cultural assimilation and end up as the exile-gone-native amongst the colonials. The resultant segregation posed a fundamental challenge to not only the Europeans, but also their half-casted offspring. For those who were born out of miscegenation, the invisible wall that divided the fixed ethnic identity became compromised yet not porous, as they were left in the wilderness to find where their allegiance should lie. The task to “know thyself” thus could be a life-long struggle to reach the elusive inner peace. This paper takes Nina Almayer, the character from Joseph Conrad's *Almayer's Folly*, as an example. Drawing on Van Gennep's concept of liminality, this paper will explore the journey Nina Almayer undertakes in forging a cultural and racial identity, analysing her negotiation of being and becoming as a process of crossing thresholds and undergoing transformation.

Keywords: Cross-cultural Encounter, Identity, Liminality.

I Introduction

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II Discussion

Published in 1895 and set in the tropical jungle of Borneo against an exotic background, Joseph Conrad's *Almayer's Folly* addresses the problematic experience of cross-cultural encounters at the turn of the twentieth century by detailing the sentimental journey the Almayers embark on to resolve their cultural and racial identity. To understand as well as appreciate the subtle condition of cultural diversity and hybridity Conrad painstaking constructs in *Almayer's Folly*, the family history of the Almayers needs to be given a detailed description. The threads that constitute the Almayers' impasse can only be gathered with a

brief visit to the protagonist's past, in which the drama of Almayer's destruction is prescribed and a significant leitmotif of ambiguous cultural identity is introduced. The epic quest Almayer embarks on for opulence and mastery began when he succumbed to the temptation of extravagance and accepts Lingard's proposal to marry his adopted Malay daughter in exchange for gold; like Faust, Almayer sells himself without hesitation. Although it is demeaning, in Almayer's view, to marry a native girl, he calculates that the match will certainly win him a share of Lingard's enormous fortune. Unable to resist the call of gold, Almayer is more than willing to sacrifice his present happiness for a distant yet rosy future in Europe. Under the shadow of Lingard, Almayer leads a parasitic life that can only be defined and sustained by the material reward Lingard promises. It becomes obvious that when the wealth Lingard guarantees fails to materialise, Almayer's fantasies collapse like a house of cards.

When colonists are lured into an isolated territory by their desire for unbounded wealth and power, they are confronted with two apparently supposing options: they can either assert their racial supremacy over the natives, or follow the path of assimilation. The consequences of either option are equally bleak. Those who distance themselves purposely from the indigenous society discover that, in their determination to maintain their ethnic superiority, they duly remain permanent outsiders and the constant hostility and potential betrayal by the natives thus become ingrained in their ventures. The latter option, however, proves to be even more unsettling. Raising the spectre of "racial contamination," the move towards assimilation was often regarded, by Europeans, as a vertical drop into degradation. These contrary courses of direction represent an inevitable and fundamental dilemma the colonists must confront when attempting to establish themselves in an alien settlement: in their quest for fame and fortunes in foreign territory, their reward is either a permanent exclusion or a free-fall into demoralisation. Cross-cultural encounters, seeing from this light, bring no honourable choice for the colonists. Being trapped in the state of in-betweenness, to be or not to be remains a difficult question.

Depicted as a European with an "Eastern mind" (Conrad, 1995, p. 11), the contributing elements of Almayer's selfhood seems to free him from the dilemma that befalls the colonists. Born and bred in the colonies, Almayer has the best chance of mastering the local intrigues whilst keeping in touch with his European roots. In effect, Almayer should have been able to exploit his assimilated capacities in his worldly pursuits. Nevertheless, boasted, proudly, by himself as "the only white man on the coast", Almayer claims racial superiority over the natives, to which Sambir responds with hatred. Yet Almayer's chronic unpopularity goes beyond the fact of his being an alien. Despite his practical insignificance as the only white man living by the river, Almayer is a physical reminder of the imperial power that overshadows the yearnings of the locals towards liberation. Ironically, on account of his interracial marriage, Almayer violates the rigid rule of racism and is tinged with demoralisation and disgrace in the eyes of other Europeans. He is treated, in spirit if not in fact, as an outcast by the European community to which he pledges his political and cultural allegiance. No longer "one of us", Almayer is banished, becoming "one of them". While his miscegenation condemns him to the status of a cultural exile among the colonials, Almayer's imagined ethnic superiority prohibits him from ever getting close to assimilation. At odds with the collective wills, both in the white and the non-white communities, Almayer inevitably finds himself permanently drifting. Eventually, Almayer is to become an isolated white man who, having lost his battle for personal aggrandisement in a far-away colony whose culture he can never penetrate, is trapped in the conflict of hopes and fears, pining away in desolation. The precarious existence Almayer leads in Sambir explains, if not

explains away, his fervent desire of returning to Europe in triumph with his beloved daughter Nina, for “[n]obody would think of her mixed blood in the presence of her beauty and his immense wealth” (Conrad, 1995, p. 5).

Although Almayer dreams of a future in Europe, he knows Europe only through the oral rendition of his mother’s tales. It is on the basis of these tales that he has constructed his dreams of Amsterdam. It is indeed a fictional and imaginary Amsterdam, but it is, nevertheless, the locus of his identity. Seeing from this perspective, while Amsterdam or Europe cannot be viewed just as the Promised Land Almayer vows to return, more importantly, it signifies Almayer’s fetishism on the original, untainted identity. In being obsessed by his racial “purity”, nevertheless, Almayer fails to recognise his daughter’s hybridity.

As a half-caste, Nina Almayer bears the burden of the interracial marriage her parents have passed on to her as their only legacy. On account of her hybridity, Nina’s life has always been suspended and questioned between the two worlds of Europe and Malaya: under Almayer’s influence, she is incessantly brought into conflict with Malay traditions, yet never is she successfully integrated into the Western community. Precipitated into a state of in-betweenness, Nina’s tormented existence is reflected in the way she is received by these two quarrelling worlds. Addressed as “Mem Putih”, the “white lady”, by the Malay community in Sambir, but treated with disdain by the colonial society in Singapore for her mixed parentage, “tolerated in both communities, but completely at home in neither”, Nina, the victimised girl, is imprisoned in the interstices of the West and the East, the artificial divide of civilisation and primitiveness, without hope of escape (McClure, 1981, p. 102). This predicament forms the heart of Nina’s bewilderment and bitterness. Nina’s parents, however, offer no relief but rather exacerbate the contradictions. As an offspring of a self-deluding father who dreams of a return to an imagined homeland and an embittered mother who aims to restore her own native values, Nina is constantly torn between the colonial snobbery and the local defiance. This enduring dilemma is conspicuous throughout the novel: Nina is presented as an ambivalent and petulant cultural orphan, limping on her own for whatever meaningful relationships she can secure.

The journey Nina endures to forge a cultural and racial identity could be better observed through the application of Arnold van Gennep’s “Rites of Passage”, that is through *separation (pre-liminal)*, *margin (liminal)*, and *reaggregation (post-liminal)*. Furthermore, employing Victor Turner’s development upon Van Gennep’s concept of liminality, Nina Almayer’s negotiation of being and becoming will be investigated as a state of transition, a state Turner calls “betwixt and between”.

Originated in Latin word *limen*, liminality means “threshold”. It is thus often used to refer to a psychological or metaphysical state, conscious or unconscious, of being on the “threshold” of or between two different established structures. In short, the state of liminality signals a process of transformation, in which the past is undermined and the future is to be made. As Robert Hampson suggests, Nina’s journey towards her identity splits over three distinct stages: her childhood in Sambir, her years in Singapore and her homecoming to Sambir (Hampson, 1992, p. 17). At the heart of the early years of Nina’s life is her love for and attachment to her father, a close relationship which, as Almayer’s faith in Lingard gradually runs dry, comes to be “the foundation of his hopes, the motive of his courage, of his determination to live and struggle” (150). This bond, however, is fractured when Lingard, “so to speak, kidnap[s] her from Brow” (35), ushering in the second stage of Nina’s life. In an

attempt to raise her “decently”, Nina is set on the course of cultural assimilation previously imposed upon her mother:

She had had Christian teaching, social education, and a good glimpse of civilised life. Unfortunately her teachers did not understand her nature, and the education ended in a scene of humiliation, in an outburst of contempt from white people for her mixed blood. She had tasted the whole bitterness of it (Conrad, 1995, p. 35).

Cast out by the “civilised” society for her “mixed blood”, the desolation Nina bears in Singapore is an experience reminiscent of her mother’s ordeal, serving as an ironic gloss on Almayer’s unceasing efforts to transplant her into his own world. Observing Almayer’s attempts to instil in Nina a European identity, Captain Ford’s blunt comment, “You can’t make her white” (Conrad, 1995, p. 26), articulates the bitter truth of the rigid regime of racial hierarchy. If Nina cannot be white, she then must be Malay. This racial, social and psychological dichotomy, mimicking Mrlow’s “us and them” mentality, creates an irreconcilable detachment in Nina from the European upbringing and threatens to take over Nina’s trajectory, which predicts a turbulent homecoming that commences the third stage of her life.

Once undergoing experiences unthinkingly, Nina now sees things consciously. As the imagined social/cultural tie has been unravelled, the physical “home” no longer provides comfort for her mind; instead, it is a disputed territory where, as the only undecided resident, her heart becomes the prized trophy for both of her parents. In her surroundings Nina sees no gleam of hope, although, owing to her instinct for survival, she contrives to maintain an equable soul by turning a blind eye to her domestic conditions and thus remains completely unperturbed in her attitude towards the outside world. By the arrival of Dain Maroola, Nina finds herself torn by the two strands of her family that constitute her being. Despite years of disenchantment, silence and solitude, Nina is now motivated to commence her sentimental, haphazard quest for identity. This conscious decision to seek where to rest her allegiance paves the way for the forthcoming clash between Nina and her father, who clings to his ascribed racial status as the last sanctuary where he can rest his pride.

In Dain Maroola, Nina “find[s] the road to freedom by obeying the voice of the new-born impulses” (Conrad, 1995, p. 119). Although Nina’s affection for Dain is genuine, it is not free from self-seeking considerations. Schwarz argues that for psychological reasons, Nina chooses Dain, a racial antitype, “as a means of passage away from a world she finds stifling and disgusting” (Schwarz, 1980, pp. 12-14). By leaving with Dain, Nina creates a fresh start for herself, more significantly, in her choice of marriage, Nina has manifestly *separated* from the European side of her heritage and announced her association with the local Malay society – an association her father had staunchly refused. Nina’s resolution shields herself from repeating the hopeless anguish of Almayer. Her action marks the first tentative step towards engaging with the Malay society, and by turning her back to the colonials and entering the luminal, she quashes the myth of immobile racial identity.

Unlike her parents who conform to the racial boundaries in acquiring their identities, it must be remembered that Nina is “forced” to establish her self-identity. Being forced to choose between the two irremediable and unbridgeable worlds of European and Malay, Nina’s elopement with Dain – a decision that is to prepare her for the new identity – or, her decision in “becoming” a Malay suggests to us the flexibility of self-identity. Robert Hampson furthers this discussion by arguing that, Nina finds her identity not through finally choosing

(or being forced to choose) her mother's world over her father's (that is, by accepting the binaries through which identity is constructed), but rather as a constant performance of identity in the interests between the different codes and traditions in which she is situated through "the overlap and displacement of domains of difference" (Hampson, 2000, p. 107). In other words, rather than reading the end of the novel in terms of Nina's finding her identity through choosing a particular originary identity, emphasis should be placed on Nina's actual behaviour in the course of narrative, which represents a continuous performance of identity through a constant negotiation of her own hybridity. In other words, rather than reading the end of the novel in terms of Nina's finding her identity through choosing a particular originary identity, emphasis could be placed on Nina's actual behaviour in the course of the narrative, which represents a continuous performance of identity through a constant negotiation of her own hybridity" (Hampson, 2000, p. 107). Thus, in the novel, Nina is described to have switched between languages. For example, her first words in the novel, although spoken to her father, are in Malay. Later, after Abdulla's visit with a marriage proposal, she speaks to her father "to his great surprise, in English". Nina's story is significant, not just because it reveals the subversion of the myth of fixed identity, but more importantly, it demonstrates that the path to self and cultural identity is not bestowed by birth, not settled once and for all, but rather is established by repeated personal quest and investment.

Granted, Conrad might not have gone far enough in the eyes of postmodernist and /or postcolonial critics in that he allocates Nina merely two choices: striving for the status of an honorary white or turning native. Moreover, the tangible contrast between Almayer and his daughter – both entrust their destinies to someone else rather than steer their own courses; while the man is apparently condemned, the woman is rescued by taking such a leap of faith. Such parallel but opposing results can make Conrad look unmistakably chivalrous and conformist to gender stereotypes. Nonetheless, I would argue that the different treatments of Almayer and Nina reflect Conrad's view on the crafting of cultural identity. For Conrad, the survival instinct of immigrants rightly dictates their strategies for coping with contingencies. Identity, though not to be cast aside lightly, remains the tale to be told by survivors, not demised. Identity is the prerogative of those mastering the art of making/remaking selfhood, not of those in thrall of fear and guilt.

III Conclusion

In liminality, the transitional state between two phases, individuals are "betwixt and between": they did not belong to the society they previously were a part of and they are not yet reincorporated into that society. For Marlow in *Heart of Darkness*, physically as well as metaphorically speaking, his trip to Africa certainly places him in a state of the liminal. Travelling from the presumed centre of the civilised world to a primitive territory in search of Kurtz, Marlow negotiates the passage attentively, yet this peregrination, having been transformed from a Gulliver-like travelogue into a spiritual voyage of self-discovery, forces on him a psychological, if not physical, reconstruction. That is to say, Marlow enters the state of liminal as soon as he begins to question the enlightened project the European colonists assigned themselves to. Similar to Marlow, Nina, Alice-like, grows and shrinks in deciding her selfhood. While Marlow's a transformed man after his journey, he returns to the fold of the civilisation he breathes in. His newfound criticism of the familiar project of enlightenment challenges but also reassures his personal membership of it. The re-aggregation, or the post-liminal, for Marlow, confirms his status in the novel as a player and an engaged member of the audience, not, as some may argue, a referee. Kurtz's last cry is a cry from the liminal, and Marlow delivers his verdict to the shores of the English Channel.

Unlike Marlow who reclaims his status as European at the end of his journey of self-discovery, Nina Almayer reaches the elusive inner peace by becoming a Malay. As a half-caste, the tormented self-searching journey Nina unfolds reveals the problematic experience of cross-cultural encounters at the turn of the twentieth century and, more importantly, how she takes the pulse of the new dawn. Nina Almayer possibly does not choose to be an exile; like many of her contemporaries, she just wants to be home.

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